

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

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UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

An Uncertainty-Oriented Production Model for Task Allocation in Electronic Document Management Systems

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Abstract

This work is devoted to solving the problem of task allocation in automated electronic document management systems. To solve the stated problem, the necessity of applying methods based on fuzzy logic and fuzzy inference systems is substantiated. A specially developed uncertainty-oriented production model is proposed. In addition, the practical application of this model is described using the example of task allocation for maintaining the register of personal data operators in the electronic document management system of the territorial department. The results obtained using the developed software complex are compared with the effectiveness of other uncertainty-based task allocation methods. A conclusion is made about the adequacy of the uncertainty-oriented production model and the necessity of its practical application in supporting decision-making for task allocation in electronic document management systems.

Keywords: electronic document management, task allocation, fuzzy logic, uncertainty-oriented production model, software complex, max–min aggregation, additive aggregation.

Introduction

At present, there is a noticeable trend toward transitioning from paper-based document processing to the active use of electronic document management systems in various areas of human activity. According to [?], electronic document management is the movement of electronic documents within an organization and the activities that ensure this movement.

For organizational management, the use of electronic document management systems enables faster access to information required for managerial decision-making, as well as operational control over execution discipline. For system users, these systems provide opportunities for rapid document search, simplification of preparation for various events and activities, and acceleration of document preparation, coordination, and approval processes.

Let us consider the electronic document management system used in the activities of the territorial bodies of . From the standpoint of protecting the rights of personal data subjects, this system solves the following main tasks [?]:

- maintaining the register of personal data operators;
- exercising control and supervision over the activities of personal data operators;
- reviewing citizens' complaints and appeals.

Among the tasks solved through this system, the most labor-intensive one is maintaining the register of personal data operators. This task includes registering operators, entering information (or changes) about operators into a unified information system, deleting operator information from the register, and providing extracts from the register upon request.

The specificity of this task lies in the requirement to register incoming applications within one day and to enter relevant information into the register no later than 15 days from the date of receipt of the application.

At the same time, the head of the department responsible for maintaining the register faces the problem of optimally allocating tasks among department employees, i.e., users of the electronic document management system. This problem is caused by the following main factors:

- uncertainty in the daily number of applications received from personal data operators;
- varying complexity of processing applications from different categories of operators;
- differences in qualification levels and current workload of executors;
- the necessity to complete tasks within deadlines established by administrative regulations.

Obviously, there is no single precise solution to this problem. Therefore, the effectiveness of the territorial body $\text{В}\mathcal{D}^{\text{TM}}$'s activities in maintaining the register of personal data operators depends on the qualifications of the department head and the correctness of decisions made when allocating tasks among executors [?].

Problem Statement of Task Allocation in an Electronic Document Management System

Let us consider the task allocation problem for maintaining the register of personal data operators [?, ?]. Assume that there is a set of N tasks with different levels of complexity: low (S_1), medium (S_2), and high (S_3). There is also a set of executors (alternatives):

$$A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\},$$

where a_1 is a chief expert specialist, a_2 is a leading expert specialist, a_3 is an expert specialist, and a_4 is a first-category specialist.

The criteria for task allocation among executors (executor characteristics) are defined as follows:

- C_1 — current workload of the executor;
- C_2 — working capacity of the executor;
- C_3 — qualification level of the executor.

It is required to solve the problem of optimal task allocation, which serves as decision support for the manager in rationally selecting an executor for each of the N tasks [?].

The decision-maker has limited time to assign an executor to a task and is not inclined

to accept a high risk of missing the established deadlines.

Although many approaches exist for solving optimization problems [?, ?, ?], under these conditions the decision-maker must consider uncertainty factors as well as the vagueness of the applied criteria. Therefore, uncertainty-based task allocation methods [?]—namely, approaches based on fuzzy logic and fuzzy inference systems [?], are required [?, ?].

Such an approach corresponds to the expert [?]'s reasoning logic in decision-making. In this work, a method based on an uncertainty-oriented production model is used to implement rational selection of alternatives [?, ?, ?].

Construction of a Task Allocation Model Based on an Uncertainty-Oriented Production Model

To solve the stated problem, we consider an approach based on constructing and applying an uncertainty-oriented production model [?, ?]. The following form of fuzzy production rules is chosen as a model for representing expert knowledge [?]:

$$\text{IF } x_1 = \bar{A}_1 \text{ AND } x_2 = \bar{A}_2 \text{ AND } \dots \text{ AND } x_n = \bar{A}_n, \text{ THEN } y = B [CF], \quad (1)$$

where x_i are input variables, \bar{A}_i are fuzzy gradations of the input variables, y is the output variable, B is a deterministic output value, and $CF \in [0, 1]$ is the certainty factor of the rule.

The model input parameters are defined as:

- x_1 — workload level of executor a_1 ;
- x_2 — workload level of executor a_2 ;
- x_3 — workload level of executor a_3 ;
- x_4 — workload level of executor a_4 ;
- x_5 — task complexity level.

The workload level of executors is determined by the number of tasks they perform simultaneously. If the number of tasks equals 20, this is considered the lower bound of maximum workload, corresponding to 100% occupancy. The model also allows workload levels to be both below and above 100%.

The workload levels are divided into three categories: low (H), medium (S), and high (B). Membership functions corresponding to these categories are shown in results.

Task complexity levels correspond to categories of personal data operators: low complexity (individuals and sole proprietors), medium complexity (legal entities), and high complexity (state and municipal authorities). Membership functions for task complexity levels are shown in results.

The certainty factor CF of each rule reflects the expert [?]'s confidence in assigning a task to a particular executor and is based on working capacity, qualifications, and workload level.

The certainty factor for assigning an executor a_i to a task of complexity level k is calculated as:

$$CF_k^i = \mu_{\bar{C}_1}(a_i) \cdot \mu_{\bar{C}_2}(a_i) \cdot \mu_{\bar{C}_{3k}}(a_i), \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_{\bar{C}_1}(a_i)$ is the utility of selecting executor a_i based on workload, $\mu_{\bar{C}_2}(a_i)$ is based on working capacity, and $\mu_{\bar{C}_{3k}}(a_i)$ is based on qualification for tasks of complexity level k .

The workload-based utility is calculated using the heuristic formula:

$$\mu_{\bar{C}_1}(a_i) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{n_i}{N}, & N \neq 0, \\ 1, & N = 0, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where n_i is the number of tasks performed by executor a_i , and $N = \sum_{i=1}^4 n_i$ is the total number of tasks.

Conclusion

The results of the conducted studies demonstrate the stability of the proposed methods and the consistency of the obtained decisions with expert opinions. An intelligent system for decision support in task allocation for maintaining the register of personal data operators has been developed. The implementation and practical application of this software complex in the electronic document management system of the functioning Administration for the Republic of Tatarstan is planned. The use of this system makes it possible to improve the quality of decisions through rational selection of effective alternatives.

References

1. Ji, Y., Shafieezadeh, A.
Robust Treatment Assignment with Uncertainty-Aware Causal Forests: Joint Optimization of Accuracy and Estimation Uncertainty. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2025, Article 130578.
2. Ping, Y., Liu, Y., Zhang, L., Wang, L., Xu, X.
Deep reinforcement learning-based multi-task scheduling in cloud manufacturing under different task arrival modes. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, 145(8), 081003, 2023.
3. Chen, H., Tian, Z.
Environmental uncertainty, resource orchestration and digital transformation: A fuzzy-set QCA approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 184–193, 2022.
4. Jin, S., Wang, B., Zhang, G., Fan, X., Jiang, S., Cao, M., Wang, Y.
Research on Low-Carbon-Emission Scheduling of Workshop under Uncertainty. *Applied Sciences*, 14(12), 4976, 2024.
5. Wang, L., Zhao, X., Wu, Z., Chen, W.
Evidence theory-based reliability optimization for cross-scale topological structures with global stress, local displacement, and micro-manufacturing constraints. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 65(1), 23, 2022.

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